

The Palestinian Experience of Business Leadership

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Abstract: The main focus of the book *“The Palestinian executive: Leadership under challenging conditions”* is to examine the leadership styles of successful senior executives and managers living and working under challenging conditions in Palestine. The authors used a cross-cultural and contextual approach to explore the impact of culture, environmental pressures, and harsh circumstances on doing business in Palestine. The book illuminates the leadership, interpersonal, and decision-making methodologies of accomplished Palestinian leaders and offers precise suggestions on nurturing prospective business leaders.

Keywords: business leadership; decision-making style; leadership; leadership style; Palestine

The book’s authors, Dr. Muna and Dr. Khoury, have used a cross-cultural and contextual approach to explore the impact of culture, environmental pressures, and difficult conditions on doing business in Palestine.¹ They examine the leadership styles of successful senior executives and managers living and working under pressing conditions in Palestine.

The book consists of four sections. The first part brings the challenging context of Palestine to the reader’s attention. It investigates the religious, cultural, and social contexts in which Palestinian business leaders function in light of environmental stress, challenges, and opportunities. The second part looks at the styles and roles of the Palestinian executives. It investigates the leadership styles of Palestinian executives and their impacts on their performance and motivation.

The third part thinks of leadership as a journey toward success. It identifies the elements of successful business leadership and offers some pieces of advice to potential executives. The book’s final part contains recommendations for developing future leaders and suggestions for future research. The text concludes with three appendices, incorporating a concise review of cross-cultural leadership literature, research methodology, statistical analysis, and the semi-structured questionnaire utilized by the authors in their research.

The book has several strengths and weaknesses in its argument. Its most remarkable strength is its research approach. The book is based on field research in the West Bank and Gaza, which involved interviewing 110 executives from 63 publicly and family-owned companies. This provides a rich and detailed understanding of the leadership styles of successful Palestinian executives.

Secondly, the book’s cross-cultural and contextual approach may be considered as a point of strength. The authors use a cross-cultural and contextual approach to explore the impact of culture, environmental pressures, and harsh circumstances on doing business in Palestine. This approach provides a nuanced understanding of the challenges facing Palestinian executives.

Thirdly, the book provides readers with specific recommendations. The authors provide specific recommendations on how to develop future business leaders in Palestine. This is a practical and useful contribution to the literature on leadership in challenging conditions. However, it is essential not to disregard the constraints of the manuscript.

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The authors primarily refrain from explicitly outlining their theoretical framework, thereby complicating the evaluation of the strength and trustworthiness of their study. Additionally, the focus of the book on the leadership approaches of successful Palestinian executives, while valuable, does not offer a comprehensive insight into business leadership within Palestine. Thirdly, the author's description of the political, economic, and social context of Palestine is limited. This makes it difficult for novice readers to fully understand the challenges facing Palestinian executives.

The book sheds light on the leadership, interpersonal, and decision-making styles of successful Palestinian executives. It enriches the field through an extensive examination of business leadership through field research. It also highlights the resilience and determination required to survive and prosper in an environment long marked by arbitrary, often deliberate, barriers. It provides first-hand evidence of the ingredients for successful business leadership, such as self-development, early responsibility, experience, and training. The book also warns of the risks of excessive social pressures from connections, cronyism, and nepotism.

The book's evidence is based on Palestinian executives' experiences and perspectives, which provides a reliable understanding of the challenges facing Palestinian businesses. The book does not directly engage with specific debates or controversies in the field of leadership studies. Nonetheless, it does tackle the distinctive obstacles Palestinian executives encounter in a milieu characterized by political, economic, and social intricacies.

The authors' study holds significance for forthcoming research in leadership studies, especially within understudied contexts like Palestine. Subsequent studies could evaluate the efficacy of the book's recommendations for cultivating future business leaders. Furthermore, researchers could delve into the potential implications of the book's discoveries for policies and practices in Palestine and other underexplored settings.

The authors' background and proficiency indicate a profound comprehension of the Palestinian environment and the hurdles confronted by business leaders in the vicinity. Their insights are shaped by their practical experience and knowledge in the business and leadership domain. They use a cross-cultural and contextual approach to explore the impact of culture, environmental pressures, and harsh circumstances on doing business in Palestine. The authors' bias is toward providing practical solutions for developing future business leaders, rather than engaging in political debates or controversies.

Compared to other literature on the same subject, this book stands out due to its concentration on the Palestinian setting and its utilization of field research to probe into the leadership methodologies of thriving Palestinian business leaders. Other works on business leadership in the Middle East typically concentrate on the broader region or specific nations like the UAE.² The broader repercussions of the book's argument for the field or society at large are substantial. The findings of the book bear vital implications for future research endeavors, particularly in less-researched areas such as Palestine.

References

1 Farid A. Muna and Grace C. Khoury, *The Palestinian Executive: Leadership under Challenging Conditions* (Burlington, Vt: Gower, 2012).

2 Deepika Gaur and Paul Katuse, "FIRO-B and Situational Leadership Model: A Correlational Context of Middle Eastern Business Leadership," *Corporate and Business Strategy Review* 3, no. 1 (2022): 144–52, <https://doi.org/10.22495/cbsrv3i1art13>.